

Studies on Free Iron Oxides and Readily Available Iron in Red, Lateritic and Alluvial Soils of West Bengal

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Manuscript received 23 July 1975 ; accepted 14 November 1975

Four different methods have been employed for estimation of free iron oxides in red, lateritic and alluvial soils of West Bengal. In case of the alluvial soils maximal free iron oxides were removed by Jackson's dithionite-citrate procedure (method-I). Deb's dithionite-tartrate (method-II) and Truog's ammonium sulphide-oxalic acid (method-III) procedures extracted almost same quantities of free iron while Deb's photolytic acid ammonium oxalate (method-IV) one removed the least amount of it. For the red and lateritic soils the above order is : method-I > method-II > method-III > method-IV.

The combined exchangeable ferrous, ferric and dilute acid soluble iron have also been determined in the above soils and effect of pH on the extraction of readily available iron by (N)-ammonium acetate have been studied. A steady decrease in the amount of iron extracted with increase in pH of the equilibrated solution was observed in all cases.

THE uncombined oxides and hydrous oxides of iron which occur freely in soil are generally termed as "free oxides of iron". This fraction of soil iron also includes those iron-containing species which exist as salts or are associated with organic matter and are easily brought into solution through simultaneous reduction and chelation. Such free iron oxides have been investigated by Tamm¹, Truog², Jeffries³, and many other workers^{4,5}. Deb⁶ employed a photolytic method involving the use of a solution containing ammonium oxalate and oxalic acid under the influence of sunlight for the determination of free iron oxides in soils and clays. In another procedure Deb used a solution of sodium dithionite in presence of a tartrate-acetate mixture while Aguilera and Jackson⁷ proposed a dithionite-citrate method for the above purpose. Several modifications of the latter procedure were suggested by Stace⁸, Coffin⁹ and others¹⁰. A method involving the use of EDTA has also been developed¹¹.

Although a highly significant correlation¹² has been established between the amount of phosphate fixed and free iron oxide content of soils it is the combined exchangeable ferrous, ferric and dilute acid soluble iron which may be considered readily available to plants. With the introduction of chelating agents like thioglycolic acid, EDTA, DTPA, etc. various availability indexes for soil iron have been proposed but acetate extractable iron at pH 3.0 is still believed to be of considerable significance to its plant availability¹³.

In the present investigation four different procedures, such as Jackson's dithionite-citrate, Deb's dithionite-tartrate, Truog's ammonium sulphide-oxalic acid and Deb's acid ammonium oxalate-sunlight methods have been employed for extraction and subsequent determination of free iron oxides with a view to find out their comparative efficiency when applied to the soils of West

Bengal. The influence of pH on the extraction of readily available soil iron by (N)-ammonium acetate solution has also been studied.

Experimental

Soil: A typical red soil, representative of the district of Purulia, a lateritic soil of Bankura and two alluvial soils—one from the district of lower Burdwan and the other from Nadia were collected from 0-16 cm. depth of the respective lands where paddy is cultivated as the principal agricultural crop. The Purulia soil was an upland one while the field from which the Bankura soil was procured was very much undulating. Both of the other two soils, belonging to old Gangetic alluvium group, were taken from comparatively low-lying fields. The red soil was sandy to sandy-loam and the lateritic soil was sandy-loam in texture while the other soils contained considerable quantities of clay.

The soils were air-dried under shade, thoroughly ground, passed through a 80-mesh sieve and subjected to subsequent investigations. Some physical and chemical properties of the soil samples are given in Table 1.

Apparatus: A Coleman Junior Absorption Photometer with green (490 nm) and red (660 nm) filters were used for the determination of iron and phosphate respectively.

A photovolt pH meter (model-85) equipped with glass and calomel electrodes was used for all pH measurements.

Reagents: All the reagents and chemicals used in the present investigation were of A. R. quality.

TABLE-1. SOIL CHARACTERISTICS

Serial No	Property Determined	Purulia Soil (R-Soil)	Bankura Soil (L-Soil)	Burdwan Soil (A-1 Soil)	Nadia Soil (A-2 Soil)
1.	Bulk density	1.42	1.35	1.20	1.16
2.	Moisture percentage	2.23	3.25	3.16	3.08
3.	Water holding capacity	40.35	41.80	48.50	49.60
4.	Clay percentage	16.75	19.60	28.45	26.30
5.	pH (1:2.5 soil-water ratio)	6.20	5.45	6.15	5.70
6.	CEC (me/100 g)	12.45	8.60	10.20	16.80
7.	Organic C (%)	0.68	0.77	0.55	0.91
8.	Total N (%)	0.09	0.06	0.12	0.09
9.	Available P ₂ O ₅ (ppm)	0.56	1.75	5.40	2.24
10.	Sesquioxide (%)	18.05	26.20	15.80	17.30
11.	Total Fe (%)	6.08	9.92	4.06	4.90
12.	Total CaO (%)	0.95	0.65	2.90	1.40

Methods: The combined exchangeable ferrous, ferric and dilute acid soluble iron content of the soil samples were determined by the ammonium acetate method according to the procedure developed by Bower and Truog and described by Jackson^{1,3} in his treatise on "Soil Chemical Analysis".

The free oxides of iron were determined by four different methods. The first one (method-I) was a modified dithionite-citrate procedure suggested by Mehra and Jackson¹⁴. Method-II was the same one developed and employed by Deb⁷ while method-III was due to Truog as described by Piper¹⁵ in his treatise on "Soil and Plant Analysis". The other method (method-IV) involved the same procedure as suggested by Deb⁶. In all the cases, estimation of iron was performed colorimetrically by ortho-phenanthroline method after extraction of the free oxides.

In order to investigate the effect of pH on the extraction of readily available iron weighed amounts of soil (10.0g) were taken in a series of polythene bottles. 50 ml of 1(N) ammonium acetate solution adjusted separately to pH 3.0, 4.0, 5.0, 6.0, 7.0, 8.0 and 9.0 respectively using requisite quantities of hydrochloric acid or caustic soda solution were added to each bottle and shaken intermittently at room temperature for 8-10 hr. The pH values of equilibrated soil suspensions were measured and the solutions filtered through Whatman No. 40 filter paper. 10 ml of each filtrate were taken in 50 ml volumetric flasks and the iron content was determined colorimetrically using o-phenanthroline as the colour-forming reagent.

Results and Discussion

The results of combined exchangeable ferrous, ferric and acid soluble iron determination are shown in

Table 2. It is found that the lateritic soil (L-Soil), which is richer in both sesquioxide and total iron contains maximal quantity of this fraction of soil iron. As we know that the ammonium acetate solution at pH 3.0 can extract all the exchangeable Fe²⁺ and most of Fe³⁺ remaining in the exchangeable form or adsorbed on soil colloids it can be concluded that the L-Soil contains a higher amount of readily available iron for plant uptake. The lower pH and wider C:N ratio of this soil indicate that ferrous iron may be quite dominant or stabilized in it. Adsorbed Fe³⁺ may also have a significant contribution to the readily available iron in lateritic soil, especially in comparison with the red soil as the former has a higher clay percentage.

Among the two alluvial soils, the one from Burdwan (A-1 soil) is found to contain a little higher amount of readily available iron although it has a lower value for total iron content. Relatively higher pH, narrower C : N ratio and lower CEC of the A-1 soil indicate that the amount of combined exchangeable ferrous and ferric iron in it should be smaller than those of the A-2 soil. Accordingly, the non-exchangeable or adsorbed ferric iron contributes more towards the total quantity of readily available iron in A-1 soil. The higher clay percentage of this alluvial soil has obviously a significant role in supplying readily available iron. Thus, in any particular group of soils, pH 3.0-extractable iron increases with the increase in clay content of the soil.

The amounts of free oxides of iron as obtained by the four different methods mentioned above are also given in Table 2.

For both of the alluvial soils maximal quantities of free oxides have been obtained in method-I where

TABLE-2

Soil	pH 3-extractable iron* (ppm)	Free Oxides of iron* (%Fe ₂ O ₃)			
		Method-I	Method-II	Method-III	Method-IV.
R-Soil	4.02	2.90	2.85	2.45	2.06
L-Soil	5.85	4.52	4.46	3.80	3.08
A-1 Soil	2.26	2.08	1.85	1.78	1.36
A-2 Soil	2.18	1.25	1.04	0.96	0.85

* Mean of three determinations for each soil

$\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_4$ has been employed as the reducing agent for Fe(III) and citrate ions at pH 7.3 as chelating agent or suppressor of hydrolytic reactions for Fe^{2+} ions. Tartrates should also serve a similar purpose, but in case of these two soils somewhat lower values for free iron oxides were obtained in method-II where tartrate was used in place of citrate. For the red and lateritic soils practically no difference between the effect of these two methods on the removal of free iron oxides was noticed. It appears that at the higher temperature (80°) used in the dithionite-citrate procedure some iron-bearing clay minerals like nontronite, biotite, chlorite, etc. are attacked while the dithionite-tartrate method carried out at 40° extracts relatively less iron from those species. From the results it seems that the alluvial soils contain larger quantities of such iron-bearing clay minerals in comparison with the red and lateritic soils used in the present investigation.

In case of alluvial soils very little difference in the amount of free iron oxides removed by the methods II and III were observed. This indicates that they contain small amounts of the crystalline oxides of iron which are known to be better attacked by the dithionite-tartrate reagent. Both dithionite-citrate and dithionite-tartrate procedures extracted larger quantities of free iron oxides in red and lateritic soils in comparison with the other two methods. Among these latter soils the lateritic one seems to contain more of the crystalline iron oxides like goethite ($\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$), lepidocrocite (an isomer of goethite) and possibly some maghemite (Fe_2O_3). The yellowish brown colour of this soil indicates the occurrence of the first two crystalline oxides while the process of lateritization through the action of organic matter and humic substances appear to favour the formation of magnetic material maghemite in it. From the colour of the Purulia red soil it seems that this soil is relatively richer in hematite—the anhydrous and crystalline form of ferric oxide.

In Truog's ammonium sulphide-oxalic acid procedure nascent H_2S is the reductant which attacks the amorphous iron oxides, colloidal hydrous oxide materials and clay particles. From the results it is obvious that in alluvial soils these are the exclusive forms of free iron while in red and lateritic soils crystalline oxides like hematite, goethite, lepidocrocite and maghemite are the dominant forms. Clay-bound free iron is present only in negligible amounts in these soils. Alluvial soils, on the other hand, contain a considerable fraction of total free iron in clay-bound state.

The photolytic method recommended by Deb extracted least amount of free iron oxides in case of all the four soils investigated. At room temperature photochemical reduction of Fe(III) is obviously a very slow process in comparison with the other methods.

In the present study pH of the oxalate solution was kept around 3.8 in order to prevent any destructive effect on the clay minerals which, obviously, made the process a still slower one. Although in Truog's procedure a slightly lower pH(3.5) was employed there was a

subsequent rise in pH as H_2S was liberated by the action of oxalic acid on sulphide ions. Some of the liberated H_2S is used up through the reaction like: $\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 + 3 \text{H}_2\text{S} = 2 \text{FeS} + 3 \text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{S}$ while a considerable fraction of it may be lost as a gas; both of the processes lead to a consequent decrease in hydrogen ion concentration of the medium. The acid ammonium oxalate-sunlight procedure is apparently ineffective or only partially effective on the crystalline oxides of iron.

From the results derived by the above four methods it can be concluded that Deb's dithionite-tartrate procedure is most reliable for the removal of free iron oxides from the alluvial, red as well as lateritic soils of West Bengal without affecting much the clay minerals or silicate structures of the soil matrix.

Variation in the amount of extracted iron with the pH of (N)-ammonium acetate extractant at equilibrium with the respective soil suspensions are shown in Table 3. The results are also depicted graphically in Fig. 1. In case of all the soils under investigation a

Fig. 1. Extraction of readily available iron as a function of pH.

○ — — ○ A-1 Soil
 ● — — ● A-2 Soil
 □ — — □ R Soil
 △ — — △ L Soil

progressive decrease in the amount of extracted iron with increase in pH of the equilibrated solution is observed. All the soils exhibited a slight rise in pH when a standard acetate buffer of pH 3.0 was used as extractant while a little fall was recorded when a buffer of pH 9.0 was incorporated. The pH of the soils themselves may be responsible for such a shift in pH.

TABLE 3

Soil	pH of the equil solution.	ppm of Fe extracted	Soil	pH of equil solution	ppm of Fe extracted
R-Soil	3.15	4.02	A-1 Soil	3.48	2.25
	4.05	3.65		4.30	1.76
	5.05	3.15		5.50	1.30
	5.95	2.75		6.32	1.02
	7.30	2.06		7.10	0.70
	8.25	1.56		7.90	0.54
	8.95	1.25		8.90	0.31
L-Soil	3.02	5.78	A-2 Soil	3.40	2.18
	3.98	5.07		4.25	1.70
	5.02	4.58		5.40	1.25
	5.85	4.15		6.30	0.96
	7.35	3.37		70.8	0.63
	8.22	3.05		7.92	0.46
	8.85	2.75		8.90	0.25

From the Fig. it is clear that both the alluvial soils behaved in a similar manner with respect to the release of readily available iron. A positive deviation (upward bend) from straight line character of the curves is observed towards the low pH region, i. e., relatively higher amounts of iron are extracted by low pH buffers. The L-soil also behaved in a manner almost analogous with the alluvial soils. A more perfect straight line behaviour is, however, shown by the R-soil which represents a negative linear relationship between the equilibrium pH and amount of iron extracted. Higher clay percentage of the lateritic soil in comparison with that of the red soil may be the reason for such a difference in behaviour between these two iron-rich soils.

The (N)-ammonium acetate buffer of pH 3.0 is not therefore a quite suitable extractant for comparing relative capacities of all types of soils with respect to the readily available fraction of soil iron. Soils containing considerable quantities of clay are, however, found to behave in a similar manner and extraction of such soils with (N)-ammonium acetate solution of pH 3.0 may provide an adequate index for plant available iron.

References

1. O. TAMM, *Medd. Stat. Skogsfors-anst.*, 1932, 27, 1.
2. E. TRUOG and M. DROSDOFF, *J. Amer. Soc. Agron.*, 1935, 27, 312.
3. C. D. JEFFRIES, *Soil. Sci. Soc. Amer. Proc.*, 1946, 11, 211.
4. R. C. MACKENZIE, *Nature*, 1949, 164, 244.
5. H. G. DION, *Soil. Sci.*, 1944, 58, 411.
6. B. C. DEB, *J. Soil. Sci.*, 1950, 1, 212.
7. N. H. AGUILERA and M. L. JACKSON, *Soil. Sci. Soc. Amer. Proc.*, 1953, 17, 359.
8. H. C. T. STACE, S. F., 1956, *Abs.*, No. 1905.
9. D. E. COFFIN, *Canad. J. Soil. Sci.*, 1963, 43, 7.
10. K. H. NIINA, *J. Jap. For. Soc.*, 1959, 41, 213.
11. P. STEFANOVITS, S. F., 1956, *Abs.*, No. 670.
12. E. G. WILLIAMS, *Chem. and Ind.*, 1957, 47, 1533.
13. M. L. JACKSON, "Soil Chemical Analysis", 1958, p. 392.
14. O. P. MEHRA and M. L. JACKSON, *Adv. Agron.*, 1960, 16, 340.
15. C. S. PIPER, "Soil and Plant Analysis", 1950, p. 234.